

Exploring Educational Needs for Developing a Mior Dadin Oriented IPAS Learning Model in Primary Schools of Sikka District

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to describe the need for developing an IPAS Learning Model Based on Mior Dadin Local Wisdom to Improve the Character of Elementary School Students. This type of research is Descriptive Qualitative Research with a Needs Assessment Approach, with data collection techniques through interviews, questionnaires, and observations which are then analyzed using qualitative and quantitative statistics. The results of the study indicate that there is an urgent need to develop an IPAS learning model that is integrated with Mior Dadin local wisdom. Teachers and students feel that the current material is less relevant to the local cultural context. Mior Dadin values such as mutual cooperation, responsibility, and love for the environment are considered capable of strengthening students' character. In addition, the absence of local-based learning guidelines is a major challenge in the teaching and learning process. These findings are an important basis for designing a contextual and meaningful IPAS learning model for students in Sikka Regency.

KEYWORDS: IPAS Learning, Mior Dadin Local Wisdom, Student Character.

INTRODUCTION

Education as an *actus humanus* has been an integral part of human life since the beginning of civilization. According to Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, education is implemented democratically, fairly, and upholds human rights and the nation's cultural values. Furthermore, Article 31 of the 1945 Constitution emphasizes that every citizen has the right to receive education, which is reinforced by the policy of compulsory basic education which is the responsibility of the central and regional governments.

In order to strengthen the quality of basic education, the Ministry of Education and Culture has stipulated Permendikbud Number 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education. This regulation emphasizes the tri-center approach of class, school culture, and society which integrates character values in the learning process. One relevant strategy is to develop a locally based curriculum to adapt education to the characteristics and needs of the region [1].

Learning Natural and Social Sciences (IPAS) in elementary schools is a strategic medium in shaping students' character through a local wisdom-based approach. According to John Hattie, learning science and social studies has a significant impact on the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Direct experience-based learning such as experiments and practical activities have been proven to be effective in strengthening students' understanding of scientific concepts. Meanwhile, in the context of social studies, a multicultural approach as proposed by James A. Banks can enrich students' insight into cultural diversity and foster an inclusive attitude [2], [3].

On the other hand, John Dewey's educational theory emphasizes the importance of direct experience in learning, as well as active interaction between students and their learning environment. Teachers also play an important role as facilitators who guide students in the process of exploration, character development, and strengthening social values. Local wisdom is an important element in strengthening character education in elementary schools. One form of local wisdom that has the potential to be integrated into social studies learning is the Mior Dadin philosophy that developed in Sikka Regency. This philosophy contains values such as Modung Mior (friendly and polite attitude), Da'an Dadin (concern for the environment), and Na'i Nalun (thrifty and wise in using resources). These values are in line with character education and can be used as a foundation in forming students' personalities who excel academically and socially [3].

However, the results of observations in several elementary schools in Sikka Regency show that the integration of Mior Dadin values in learning is still very limited. Of the 336 elementary schools, only 19 schools (5.65%) in Doreng District have implemented Mior Dadin local wisdom-based learning. Students' understanding of these values is still minimal, and teachers experience

difficulties in linking science and natural sciences material with the local cultural context. Several teachers have tried to insert folklore into learning, but the integration of concepts between science and local values is still not optimal. In addition, the lack of relevant learning resources and parental involvement in the process of forming student character are also challenges that need to be overcome. In this context, it is important to conduct an in-depth study of educational needs at the elementary school level in order to develop a science and natural sciences learning model that is oriented towards Mior Dadin. This model is expected to be able to present learning that is more contextual, meaningful, and rooted in local culture, so that it can form strong student character and create holistic and sustainable education in Sikka Regency.

LITERATURE

Local wisdom is usually passed down from one generation to the next through word of mouth. Local wisdom is found in folklore, proverbs, songs, and folk games (Pornpimon et al., 2014). Local wisdom as a knowledge discovered by a particular local community through a collection of experiences in trying and integrated with an understanding of the culture and natural conditions of a place. Local wisdom according to Subadio (2008) is generally considered the same as culture/identity which is interpreted as the cultural identity of the nation. Meanwhile, Kemp (2009) said that local wisdom is all forms of knowledge, beliefs, insights, and customs/ethics that guide humans in their behavior in an ecological community [4], [5]. The educational perspective on local wisdom is an important aspect in the context of character education in Indonesia. Local wisdom refers to the knowledge, culture, traditions, and values that develop in a particular society or community. Integration of local wisdom in inclusive education contains several philosophical aspects: Identity and Recognition: Local wisdom plays an important role in shaping individual and community identity. Involving local wisdom in education provides recognition of local identity and culture, which in turn can increase students' self-esteem and sense of belonging [6].

Relevance and Significance: Integration of local wisdom in education can increase the relevance of learning to students' daily lives. Subject matter that is linked to local realities is easier for students to understand and relate to, so that learning becomes more meaningful. Intercultural Understanding and Tolerance: Teaching students about local wisdom also opens the door to understanding and appreciating other cultures. This can foster a sense of tolerance and mutual respect for cultural differences in a diverse society. Contextual Learning: Local wisdom can be integrated into learning to provide a more real and tangible context for students. The use of local examples in lessons can help students relate abstract concepts to concrete situations [6].

Preservation of Cultural Heritage: Integration of local wisdom in education can also help in maintaining and preserving the cultural heritage that exists in society. This is important in preventing the erosion of traditional cultural values. Empowering Local Communities: Involving local communities in education can result in a strong partnership between schools and communities. This can create a climate that supports the comprehensive development of students and strengthen the relationship between formal education and the surrounding reality [7]. Local wisdom-based education can be used as a medium to preserve the potential of each region. Local wisdom must be developed from regional potential. Because regional potential is the potential of specific resources owned by a particular region. Students who come to school cannot be likened to an empty glass, which can be filled easily. Students are not like plasticine that can be shaped according to the teacher's wishes. They already have cultural values formed from their family and community environments. Wise teachers must be able to integrate local wisdom values into the learning process. Local wisdom-based education will certainly be successful if teachers understand the insight of local wisdom itself. Teachers who do not understand the meaning of local wisdom tend to be less sensitive to local cultural diversity. As a result, they are less able to create learning that respects cultural diversity and the specifics of the level of PDBK needs for each type of disorder [7].

METHOD

Sample and procedure

This study uses a qualitative approach, qualitatively it is explained how the analysis of the needs of developing a local wisdom-based science learning model mior dadin to improve the character of school students as a reference in local wisdom-based character education mior dadin science learning for grade V Elementary Schools in Sikka Regency. The data source in this study was obtained by considering aspects and indicators related to the implementation of local wisdom-based science learning mior dadin is to find out the description of the analysis of the needs for the development of the model can be seen from the results of interviews with grade V teachers. The needs analysis was carried out to obtain various initial information to capture objective conditions in the field

regarding the implementation of character education services in schools, which were used as a basis and used to plan or design theoretical-hypothetical models. This activity was carried out with an initial survey through observation and interviews with class teachers and principals. Other activities are reviewing concepts, reviewing related research results and conducting Focus Group Discussions (FGD). FGD activities include:

1. An initial survey was conducted to obtain actual and factual events related to the Implementation of character services in schools.
2. Reviewing the concept through literature review, to obtain theoretical information related to science learning and local wisdom mior dadin.
3. Empirical studies are conducted with research results related to character education and relevant local wisdom concepts. Activities that are no less important in this empirical study are conducting interviews, distributing questionnaires and conducting FGDs to obtain information on whether or not the target audience needs the development of a science learning implementation model based on local wisdom mior dadin

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Based on the results of preliminary studies in the form of observations and interviews, data has been found related to the development of the local wisdom-based science and environmental science learning model mior dadin to improve the character of students at SDN Wegoknatar and SDN Wolonbue, including the following:

1. Analysis of student needs

The series of activities in developing this model began with a needs analysis at the school. The researcher determined the results of the needs analysis through a preliminary study at SDN Wegoknatar and SDN Wolonbue.

Based on observations during the learning process and interviews with teachers who also teach the subject, information was obtained that students have low local character which is shown in daily behavior such as low ability to help friends, lack of concern for cleaning the school environment and being lazy to study. To overcome this problem, teachers have made efforts to foster students such as appealing and advising, but these coaching efforts have not been optimally successful because students continue to repeat the same treatment. In addition, the handling is not on target so that the problems actually experienced by students are not handled properly. The teacher said that the development of the local wisdom-based IPAS learning model mior dadin is considered important because it can be an alternative to teaching character indicators for students at SDN Wegoknatar and SDN Wolonbue

This is in line with the results of observations made by researchers in the classroom in the form of small groups of 6 groups consisting of 7 people each group in order to continue the offline teaching process carried out by the teacher. During the learning process, it was seen directly that some did not want to help each other with their friends during the learning process, there was also a lack of awareness of maintaining the classroom environment so that it was dirty and even some students were less active in the learning process.

The results of the observations carried out were then followed up by distributing a student character questionnaire that was made simply by the researcher. The formulation of the questionnaire refers to the indicators of student character that were put forward. The questionnaire was distributed to all 41 students in grade 5 in both elementary schools, 28 people or 68.3% had low character which can be seen from the low aspect of concern for friends, cleanliness of the classroom environment and yard and learning aspects. These results indicate that serious efforts are needed to address this problem.

Based on the description of the results of the needs analysis for students through interviews, observations and direct distribution of questionnaires, a general picture is obtained that there is no model that can be used to introduce students to characters that are in accordance with the needs of students. So it is necessary to conduct development research that can produce a product in the form of a local wisdom-based learning model based on the local wisdom of mior dadin to improve student character and efforts to overcome the problems experienced above which are expected to strengthen student character such as the values of sharing, cooperation, helping each other, caring for the environment and diligent learning as provisions for the future. Based on the summary results that have been presented above, the researcher concludes that the development of a local wisdom-based science learning model mior dadin is very much needed by students of SDN Wegoknatar and SDN Wolonbue.

2. Teacher Needs Analysis

As for the analysis of teacher needs, a teacher must know all kinds of shortcomings in the learning process starting from the beginning of teaching and shortcomings in the application of learning methods/models. Therefore, teachers should conduct initial investigations and conduct interviews with 2 science teachers at SDN Wegoknatar and SDN Wolonbue to find out initial information about the character of the students. Based on the results of the interview with one of the science teachers at SDN Wegoknatar, Mrs. Maria Kartini, S.Pd that:

Learning so far has not been very contextual by combining elements of local wisdom, especially the local wisdom of mior dadin so that students do not understand local culture because the material given seems to be only on one learning source which is the main content of science.

The same thing was also conveyed by another teacher, Mrs. Cisilia Sika, S.Pd, a science teacher at SDN Wolonbue, that: The character of students is decreasing where students do not show the values of sharing, cooperation, honesty, helpfulness, sweeping the yard and being lazy to learn. So that efforts are needed to improve student character through the science learning model. Based on the information and observations of researchers, that students especially in SDN Wegoknatar and SDN Wolonbue have less good characters, so they need to be improved, especially in the importance of characters such as implementing the values of sharing, cooperation, honesty and helping each other, cleaning the environment and being diligent in studying. This shows that there is a need for innovations in new, more creative learning models that can further instill the values of local wisdom mior dadin to improve the character of students at SDN Wegoknatar and SDN Wolonbue

Discussion

Based on the results of the study in the needs analysis phase, it can be concluded that teachers and students need a local wisdom-based science learning model mior dadin by assessing students' character in the implementation of science learning and outside the implementation of learning. As previously explained, the curriculum revision has been implemented for the past 6 years. However, the implementation of science learning based on local wisdom, especially local wisdom mior dadin, has never been adapted into the current curriculum. This means that teachers have not innovated and developed the implementation of science learning in elementary schools. In other words, the implementation of science learning has not paid attention to aspects of student character, and in the process of its implementation it still uses conventional and non-contextual learning methods. In general, in science learning, several tendencies of problems were found when researchers conducted a preliminary study. the low character behavior of students, it appears that students still do not apply the values of sharing, cooperation, helping each other, planting trees, cleaning the environment and studying diligently as a manifestation of student character values. In addition, teachers have not fully guided students to apply character in the learning process, both in and outside the classroom. This is because teachers have limitations in developing an appropriate and contextual model, method and strategy in implementing character in science learning. This fact is very contrary to 21st century learning which instills the importance of character education for students. The challenges and opportunities in 21st century education are expected to be a benchmark in instilling character education, which clearly will be many challenges faced by the world of education [8], [9].

The implementation of local wisdom values mior dadin in the science learning process is considered important to maintain the existence of culture in relations between members of society there are elements that contain high philosophical values. They make it a stick to live their daily lives. Science learning can introduce, instill insight into caring for the natural environment and also maintain good relations with other humans.

One of the important stages in this research and development is the needs analysis phase. This phase aims to collect and identify the needs of users (teachers and students) before developing a product. This phase is considered important because it is the basis and benchmark for designing a good learning model product that suits the needs of its users. Needs analysis is carried out in the process of designing the developed teaching module. In this context, there is a gap between reality and the desired expectations in achieving student character. Needs analysis can be interpreted as a way or method used to determine the difference between reality and existing desires. In this case, the expected conditions are the embodiment of ideal conditions while reality is a current event that is truly real and does not yet match what is expected [10]. Basically, needs analysis is carried out with the aim of providing opportunities and opportunities between the applicable curriculum and the current needs of students. This means that researchers develop learning models that are in accordance with the needs of their users which of course do not conflict with the applicable curriculum. Joshi (2021) emphasized that the current curriculum must also be adjusted to the needs of users so that both can go hand

in hand and complement each other. Needs analysis has a very important role in helping the learning implementation process because it is a basic principle in a student-centered learning system. In other words, learning must be responsive to the needs of students. Furthermore, needs analysis must be linked to the learning context which includes the curriculum, textbooks or textbooks, obstacles faced and the implementation of learning [11], [12], [13].

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and description of the needs of teachers and students, in learning science through the results of interviews, observations, and document analysis, it is necessary to develop a science learning model based on Mior Dadin's local wisdom to improve student character which produces a product in the form of a model book, model guide book, and teaching module and Student Worksheet (LKPD).

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